

Science Motivation and Process Skills of Grade 6 Learners In Lupon, West District

Reymon T. Alegro

Abstract. This study aimed to determine the relationship between science motivation and science process skills of grade 6 learners in Lupon, West District, Davao Oriental. A quantitative descriptive-correlational research design was employed to assess five domains of science motivation: intrinsic motivation, career motivation, self-determination, self-efficacy, and grade motivation; and their influence on five core science process skills, namely observing, measuring, inferring, experimenting, and communicating. The findings revealed that science motivation was rated "Extremely Extensive," with intrinsic and grade motivation ranking highest. Likewise, learners demonstrated "Extremely Extensive" science process skills, particularly in measuring and observing. Pearson correlation analysis showed a very strong positive and statistically significant relationship between science motivation and science process skills. Furthermore, regression analysis identified grade motivation, self-efficacy, career motivation, and intrinsic motivation as significant predictors of learners' process skills. These findings highlight the vital role of science motivation in the development of learners' scientific competencies. Teachers and school leaders are encouraged to integrate motivation-enhancing strategies in classroom instruction and resource planning to improve scientific engagement and skill development. This study also offers valuable insights for curriculum planners, education stakeholders, and future researchers focusing on the intersections of motivation and performance in science education.

KEY WORDS

1. Science motivation 2. science process skills 3. grade motivation

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1. Introduction

Science process skills is challenging even up to this 21st century era because there are still insufficiencies of substantial preparation and resources to create hands-on learning experiences that build critical thinking in learners. Science motivation towards learners affects their enthusiasm and engagement of learning science process skills. If educators lack the drive and support to create interactive learning environments, it becomes difficult for learners to acquire and sharpen essential science process skills through compelling experiments and activities. Addressing these obstacles is key to improving science motivation among educators and learners, ultimately leading to a more effective science education. In Indonesia, science process skills education can be a difficult endeavor for educators as they direct the complicated setting of facilitating hands-on learning practices and developing critical thinking abilities in learn-

ers. One significant struggle is the need for extensive preparation and resource allocation to design and execute engaging experiments or activities that effectively demonstrate these skills. Many teachers find themselves grappling with limited access to laboratory equipment, materials, or time constraints, hindering their ability to provide comprehensive and practical learning experiences (Sulistri, 2019). A study by Duban, Aydođdu, and Yüksel (2019) in Turkey explored classroom teachers' perspectives on science laboratory practices. The constraints highlighted that limited access to laboratory equipment and materials, along with time constraints, impedes teachers' ability to conduct effective hands-on science activities. These limitations contribute to reduced student motivation and engagement in laboratory work, thereby affecting the development of SPS. In Nigeria, the effective development of science process skills (SPS) among learners is significantly hindered by insufficient laboratory facilities and instructional resources. According to Amadi and Amadi (2022), the lack of essential laboratory equipment compels teachers to depend largely on theoretical instruction rather than engaging learners in practical, hands-on scientific activities. This pedagogical limitation negatively affects students' motivation to learn science and restricts their ability to internalize and apply scientific concepts through experiential learning. Likewise, in Pakistan, fostering science process skills among students remains a major educational challenge due to reliance on conventional teaching practices and limited infrastructure. A study conducted by Haider and Muhammad (2020) in the Sargodha District demonstrated that students exposed to traditional lecture-based instruction showed weaker proficiency in SPS compared to those who participated in inquiry-based learning environments. The researchers emphasized the need for adopting active learning strategies and providing sufficient instructional resources to enhance learners' motivation and skill development in science. In the Philippine context, enhancing science process skills among Filipino learners has become a primary focus of the reformed science education agenda for the 21st century. A major aim is to cultivate lifelong learners who are confident and equipped with the necessary skills, attitudes, and competencies to succeed in increasingly complex societies. Central to achieving this is the strategic motivation of learners. According to the Science Education Institute of the Department of Science and Technology, one of the foremost goals of the Philippine science education framework is to strengthen learners' science process skills aligned with 21st-century learning demands (Balmeo, 2022). Also in the Philippines, particularly in Iloilo City, the development of science process skills (SPS) among junior high school learners remains a pressing concern due to the overreliance on teacher-led demonstrations instead of hands-on laboratory experiences. This issue is largely driven by constraints such as limited school resources, overcrowded classrooms, and lack of access to adequate laboratory equipment. As a result, learners are deprived of opportunities to actively engage in scientific investigations that are vital for nurturing inquiry-based thinking and critical analysis. Mirana (2019) found that despite students in various Philippine schools exhibiting a generally positive attitude toward science, their SPS remained underdeveloped due to minimal use of inquiry-oriented teaching approaches and poor laboratory infrastructure. Further, in Eastern Samar, Philippines, the advancement of science process skills (SPS) among Grade 11 students is significantly impeded by the scarcity and underutilization of laboratory resources. A study conducted by Noroña (2021) across three secondary schools in the region revealed that the limited availability of essential laboratory equipment forces educators to rely predominantly on theoretical instruction, thereby depriving students of crucial hands-on scientific experiences.

This lack of practical engagement not only diminishes students' motivation to learn science but also hampers their ability to develop and apply SPS effectively. The findings highlight the pressing need for educational reforms that focus on improving laboratory resources and adopting inquiry-based instructional strategies to promote scientific literacy and enhance learners' problem-solving abilities. Locally, in Lupon West District, Davao Oriental Division, while no study on the status of science motivation and process skills of grade 6 learners have been conducted, however, based on reports in some schools of Lupon, West District, in Davao Oriental Division, science motivation was inadequate which impacted the achievement of process skills of grade 6 learners. Because of this, Science teachers in the Elementary Department share common problems on their struggles in teaching Science competencies particularly the achievement of Science process skills. The proponent opted to select 5 schools within Lupon, West District, in Davao Oriental Division. The result of the study could serve as a significant basis for the school's planning and budget prioritization, particularly in the allocation of funds for science-related resources, materials, equipment, and training. By identifying the specific needs and gaps in learners' motivation and process skills, the school may better allocate resources to enhance science instruction. Ultimately, the findings are expected to contribute to the improvement of science teaching and learning, ensuring that the school is able to provide adequate support to achieve the desired development of science process skills among Grade 6 learners..

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study —This research is anchored in Piaget's (1964) Constructivist Learning Theory, which posits that learning is an active, dynamic process wherein individuals build their own understanding of the world through interaction with their environment and experiences. In the realm of science education, this theory

emphasizes that learners construct knowledge by engaging meaningfully with scientific concepts, reflecting on their experiences, and making sense of new information through personal interpretation and exploration. This approach has a direct connection to science motivation and the development of science process skills among learners. When applied to science education, constructivism encourages learners to explore, experiment, and draw their own conclusions, promoting intrinsic motivation. This heightened motivation drives students to participate in hands-on activities, engage in collaborative projects, and actively question and refine their understanding of which are key components of science process skills. Through constructivist practices, learners are encouraged to make connections between scientific concepts and their real-world applications, thereby deepening their engagement and fostering critical thinking. The active involvement that constructivism promotes is essential for cultivating skills such as observation, hypothesis testing, and data analysis, as it aligns with the idea that learning is most effective when students are motivated by their curiosity and interest. Therefore, the constructivist approach emphasizes the connection between science motivation and the development of science process skills, demonstrating that when learners are motivated to explore and understand, they are more likely to develop the foundational skills needed for scientific inquiry. Another relevant theory that supports the relationship between science motivation and the development of science process skills is Vygotsky's Socio-Cultural Theory (1978). This theory highlights the importance of social interaction and cultural context as central elements in the learning process. It posits that learners actively construct knowledge through meaningful engagement with others particularly through interactions with teachers, peers, and the wider community. In the context of science education, this theory closely aligns with the role of science

motivation in enhancing learners' development of science process skills. When students engage in collaborative learning environments, they are given the opportunity to exchange ideas, ask questions, and receive feedback. These social interactions not only promote deeper conceptual understanding but also stimulate interest, confidence, and motivation to learn science. Furthermore, Vygotsky introduced the concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), which refers to the range of tasks a learner can perform with guidance. Within this zone, motivation and skill development are enhanced through scaffolding and structured support. Thus, Socio-Cultural Theory offers a strong foundation for understanding how social environments influence learners' motivation and provide the conditions necessary for developing critical scientific competencies through active participation and cooperative learning. Motivated learners are more likely to participate actively in group experiments, discussions, and other collaborative activities that are crucial for building science process skills such as observation, analysis, and experimentation. Through social and cultural contexts, learners gain a better understanding of the relevance of science to their lives, increasing their engagement and willingness to practice and refine science process skills.

Thus, socio-cultural theory underscores the importance of a supportive social environment in fostering science motivation, ultimately leading to more effective acquisition of science process skills among learners. As shown in Figure 1, this study examines two key variables: the independent variable, science motivation, and the dependent variable, science process skills. Science motivation encompasses five components: intrinsic motivation, career motivation, self-determination, self-efficacy, and grade motivation. These elements influence how learners engage with science, driving their interest, persistence, and performance in scientific tasks. On the other hand, science process skills refer to essential cognitive and practical abilities that learners use to conduct scientific inquiry and solve problems. These include observing, measuring, inferring, experimenting, and communicating. Mastery of these skills allows students to explore, understand, and explain natural phenomena effectively. By analyzing the relationship between science motivation and science process skills, this study aims to determine how motivational factors contribute to the development of critical scientific competencies, equipping learners to succeed academically and apply these skills in real-world contexts.

2. Methodology

This section presents the research design, respondents of the study, research instrument, data gathering procedures, and methods of data analysis employed to address the research questions and achieve the study's objectives.

2.1. Research Design—The researcher utilized a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design to collect relevant data, ideas, and information associated with the study. It is considered descriptive as it aimed to assess the levels of both laboratory resources and science process skills. The correlational aspect was applied to explore the possible relationship

between science motivation and science process skills without manipulating any variables. As defined by Bhandari (2020), quantitative research involves strategies focused on measuring and analyzing data using numerical methods. This type of research follows a deductive reasoning approach, often grounded in empiricist and positivist traditions, where existing theories

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study

are tested. Since the study did not involve altering any independent variable, it falls under a non-experimental design. In this approach, researchers simply observe and measure variables as they exist in real-world settings rather than introducing any experimental treatment. This method allowed the researcher to gather statistical data objectively and draw conclusions about the natural relationship between the learners' science motivation and their science process skills. It also helped identify how existing laboratory resources may contribute to developing these essential scientific competencies. According to Myers and Well (2013), correlational research explores the influence of one variable on another and seeks to identify potential relationships between variables, though it does not necessarily establish direct cause-and-effect. In the context of this study, the researcher examined the connection between science motivation and science process skills among learners. The primary goal was to determine whether a statistically significant relationship exists between these two variables. This study specifically focused on identifying patterns and associations,

rather than manipulating variables. Therefore, the descriptive-correlational design was deemed appropriate, as it allowed for the analysis of respondents' behaviors and experiences in a natural educational setting. No experimental treatment or controlled environment was applied; instead, the study relied on naturally occurring data. This approach enabled the researcher to measure and describe the current state of both variables while assessing how one may relate to the other.

2.2. *Ethical Consideration—*

2.3. *Research Respondents—*The participants in this study consisted of 50 public elementary school teachers from Lupon West District, Davao Oriental, Region XI, Philippines. These respondents were chosen using the stratified random sampling technique. As explained by Shi (2019), stratified sampling involves dividing a population into distinct subgroups, or strata, and then selecting samples from each subgroup. This method is particularly effective when the researcher recognizes that the population includes diverse segments that may vary in characteristics or perspectives. By applying

this technique, the study ensured representation across relevant subgroups within the teaching population, thereby enhancing the accuracy and reliability of the findings. By using this method, researchers made more precise estimates about the population and draw conclusions that are more likely to apply across different groups within the population. Thus, stratified sampling provides a robust framework for connecting with a diverse range of research respondents, yielding more comprehensive and representative findings. To determine the appropriate respondents for this study, specific inclusion criteria were applied. The main criterion was to select individuals who could provide relevant and reliable information aligned with the objectives of the research. Therefore, only permanent and regular public elementary school teachers with a minimum of five years of teaching experience were included. Additionally, participation was limited to those who voluntarily signed the Informed Consent Form (ICF). These qualified respondents were then provided with the survey questionnaires. Furthermore, the scope of the study was confined strictly to addressing the variables and concerns outlined in the research questions. As such, factors beyond the identified scope such as the teachers' performance ratings were not included in the analysis. This delimitation ensured a focused examination of

The second part of the instrument is the Science process skills. This questionnaire was adapted from Akani (2015) indicated with observing, measuring, inferring, experimenting, and communicating. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the respondents made use the 5-Likert scale which are as fol-

The questionnaires underwent content validation by a panel of three experts to ensure their relevance and appropriateness for the study. Additionally, the instruments were subjected to a

the relationship between science motivation and science process skills without introducing extraneous variables.

2.4. Research Instrument—The study utilized questionnaires adapted from various existing studies and revised to align with the specific context of the respondents. The instrument was composed of two main parts. The first part focused on assessing science motivation and was adapted from the study titled "Assessing Science Motivation for College Students: Validation of the Science Motivation Questionnaire II using the Rasch-Andrich Rating Scale Model" by Hye et al. (2018). Modifications were made to ensure relevance and appropriateness for elementary school teachers as respondents. In responding to the questionnaire, the participants were instructed to use a five-point Likert scale, with the following response options: 5 – Strongly Agree, 4 – Agree, 3 – Somewhat Agree, 2 – Disagree, and 1 – Strongly Disagree. To assess the level of availability and utilization of laboratory resources, the researcher applied a range of means as a basis for interpretation. This served as a guide in classifying and describing the responses according to specific levels, ensuring consistent and meaningful analysis of the data related to resource accessibility and usage in the science learning environment.

lows: 5–Strongly Agree, 4–Agree, 3–Somewhat Agree, 2–Disagree, 1–Strongly Disagree. As a guide in determining the level process skills of grade 6 learners as believed by the teachers, the researcher will make use of the range of means, description and interpretation as presented below:

pilot test conducted in the researcher's school to assess their validity and reliability. The feedback, corrections, and recommendations provided by the experts during the validation pro-

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation of Science Motivation

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Extremely Extensive	It means that Science motivation is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	Very Extensive	It means that Science motivation is oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	It means that Science motivation is sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Slightly Extensive	It means that Science motivation is seldom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	It means that Science motivation is never evident.

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation of Science Process Skills

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Extremely Extensive	Science Process skills is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	Very Extensive	Science Process skills is oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Science Process skills is sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Slightly Extensive	Science Process skills is seldom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Science Process skills is never evident.

cess were carefully considered and integrated into the final version of the instruments to en-

hance their clarity, accuracy, and effectiveness.

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure*—Steps undergone by the researcher in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire.

Permission to Conduct the Study

Prior to conducting the study, the researcher obtained the necessary approvals. An endorsement letter was secured from the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. This endorsement was attached to the permission letters addressed to the school principals of the identified public elementary schools in Lupon West District, Davao Oriental. These documents formally requested

authorization to carry out the data collection and ensure ethical compliance with institutional and field protocols. The letters were personally brought by the researcher to the principals of the schools where the study was conducted. The researcher first appears in the office of the principals in the second week of November 2024. After the approval from the respective offices were granted, the researcher then proceeded to the distribution and retrieval of the survey questionnaires. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire Following the approval to conduct the study, the researcher proceeded with the distribution of the research instruments to

the selected respondents. The data collection was conducted during School Year 2024–2025. Prior to administering the questionnaires, the purpose, objectives, and benefits of the study were clearly explained to all participants to ensure informed and voluntary participation. The confidentiality of their responses was also emphasized to encourage honest and accurate answers. The questionnaires were administered simultaneously and distributed personally by the researcher to ensure clarity of instructions and consistency in the process. Respondents were given sufficient time to answer the instrument at their own pace, with no pressure to rush. Assistance was provided when necessary to address any queries regarding the items. The completed questionnaires were then collected, organized, and reviewed for completeness. After data collection, all responses were encoded, tabulated, and subjected to appropriate quantitative statistical analyses to determine the relationships between the variables under investigation and to draw relevant conclusions from the findings.

Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data
After retrieving the completed questionnaires, the responses were tallied and organized based on each indicator. The data were then encoded and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the results, while inferential analyses, such as correlation and regression, were applied to examine the relationships between variables and test the study's hypotheses.

Research Ethics

The researcher strictly followed the required protocols and standard guidelines in conducting the study, particularly those related to ethical considerations in managing participants and handling data. The survey questionnaires, along with proper attribution to original sources, were submitted for review and evaluation. Upon receiving approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of

the research process, which included data collection and analysis.

Informed Consent

The researcher sought permission from the respondents through a written informed consent. Participants were adequately informed about the objective of the study, and clear explanations were provided to help them fully understand the purpose of their involvement, allowing them to decide freely whether to take part. It was emphasized that their participation was entirely voluntary. If they chose not to participate, no pressure or coercion was applied. The researcher also took necessary steps to ensure the respondents' emotional and psychological safety throughout the study. A signed consent form was obtained from each participant as proof of their willingness to participate. The respondents were also informed that the research aimed to examine the factors that either hinder or support teacher commitment, as influenced by the conditions within the learning environment. **Vulnerability of Research Participants** The respondents of this study were public elementary school teachers who are not classified as part of a vulnerable population, as all participants were of legal age. However, the researcher acknowledged the potential for psychological vulnerability and took appropriate precautions. Participation in the survey was arranged at a time convenient for the respondents to minimize any disruption or discomfort. Additionally, the researcher ensured that all information provided by the participants was treated with strict confidentiality and handled responsibly throughout the study. **Privacy and Confidentiality** This study complied with the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012, ensuring that the information gathered could not be traced back to the individual participants. The researcher guaranteed that the identities of the respondents were fully protected throughout the study. No personal data was shared or disclosed without the explicit consent of the participants. To maintain confidentiality, access

to the survey responses was restricted solely to the researcher. In protecting the respondents' privacy, it was ensured that no other individual had access to the data. Once the necessary data were collected and analyzed, the researcher permanently disposed of the survey forms and results, thereby safeguarding against any possibility of tracing the data back to the original sources. These measures were taken to uphold ethical standards and protect the integrity and privacy of all participants involved in the study.

Risk, Benefits and Safety During the administration of the survey questionnaires, the researcher clearly and thoroughly explained to the participants the nature of their involvement, including the study's purpose, benefits, and the confidentiality of their responses, as indicated in the online survey form. Respondents were encouraged to freely raise any questions or concerns regarding the study. The researcher ensured that no harm physical, psychological, or emotional would result from their participation. The questionnaires and interview guides used in the study were carefully reviewed to avoid any offensive, degrading, or inappropriate content. The study was strictly academic in nature and focused only on gathering information relevant to the research topic, without requiring respondents to disclose personal or sensitive details. To reduce any inconvenience, the researcher allotted sufficient time for respondents to complete the questionnaires. Moreover, participants were informed of their right to skip any questions that made them uncomfortable and were assured that they could withdraw from the study at any point, especially if they experienced psychological or emotional distress related to the questions.

Justice To ensure fairness and eliminate bias in the selection of participants, the researcher treated all potential respondents equally, regardless of whether they chose to participate in the survey. No favoritism or discrimination was practiced in identifying respondents. All individuals who met the inclusion criteria—being

a permanent public elementary school teacher with more than five years of teaching experience in the purposively selected schools were considered eligible. Throughout the data collection process, the researcher was mindful of the respondents' time and ensured minimal disruption to their regular activities. As a gesture of gratitude for their participation, the researcher prepared tokens of appreciation, which consisted of assorted souvenirs. These tokens were carefully packed and sent to the respondents via courier service, maintaining proper handling and confidentiality.

Transparency To ensure transparency in the conduct of this research, all forms of communication related to the study were carried out with honesty and integrity. The researcher carefully followed the procedures outlined in the methodology to protect the well-being of the participants and to maintain ethical standards. All essential documents supporting the data analysis were properly documented and included in the study. The researcher clearly explained the extent of the respondents' participation, ensuring they understood their role in the research process. Additionally, objectivity was upheld throughout the data analysis and interpretation, ensuring that findings were presented accurately, without bias or manipulation.

Qualification of the Researcher The researcher took measures to ensure that respondents' answers remained unbiased and were not influenced by any external factors, including potential conflicts of interest. The results of the study will be made accessible to respondents and school administrators from the participating schools, provided that proper procedures are followed to maintain the confidentiality and anonymity of participants. Acknowledgment is given to all individuals who contributed to the successful completion of this research. A final copy of the study's findings will be submitted to the Division Office of Davao Oriental, allowing respondents and stakeholders to utilize the results for academic reference, professional

development, and future research purposes.

Adequacy of Facilities

The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment, ensuring that appropriate learning materials were readily available throughout the conduct of the study. All activities were completed within the scheduled timeframe set by the researcher to maintain consistency. To ensure accuracy in data collection, the responses were carefully encoded during times when the researcher was alert and focused, minimizing the possibility of encoding errors. The data analysis and interpretation were carried out with precision and aligned closely with the study's objectives. The results served as a valid basis for assessing the adequacy of the findings and ensuring the integrity of the research pro-

cess.

Community Involvement

Engaging the community at every stage of the research process from planning to dissemination is considered the best practice. In line with this, the researcher prioritized community involvement in shaping the research agenda, selecting appropriate methods suited to their context, and determining how the results would be utilized. The insights and findings generated from this study will be shared with the community through organized events such as gatherings, forums, and conferences, ensuring that the participants and stakeholders are informed and empowered to apply the results in meaningful ways.

2.6. Data Analysis—The following statistical tools were employed by the researcher to analyze and interpret the data collected in the study:

Mean

This was useful in measuring the level of science motivation and science process skills. Mean and standard deviation are descriptive statistics that measure how the score clustered

and scattered, respectively.

Pearson-R

This was utilized to describe the significance of the relationship among science motivation and science process skills.

Linear Regression Analysis

Was applied to determine which domains of science motivation significantly influence science process skills.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter discussed the findings of this study. They were thoroughly discussed, analyzed, and interpreted.

3.1. Extent of Science Motivation —Science motivation plays a vital role in shaping how learners engage with scientific concepts, tasks, and experiences. It reflects the degree to which students are driven by interest, curiosity, and personal goals in learning science. Understanding the extent of science motivation among learners provides valuable insight into their attitudes, behaviors, and academic performance in the subject. Presented in Table 1 are data on the Summary of the Science Motiva-

tion. The overall mean rating of 4.23, which is Extremely Extensive and always evident, is distributed by the indicators. They were presented with the corresponding mean as follows: intrinsic motivation (4.52), career motivation (4.21), self-determination (4.16), self-efficacy (4.11), and grade motivation (4.14). Two out of five of these indicators have descriptive equivalents of extremely extensive. The findings of the study agree with Kennepohl (2021), who emphasized the importance of science motiva-

tion in promoting student engagement in investigative scientific experiences. He asserted that a motivating environment encourages learners to explore phenomena using their own curiosity and observational skills. This directly supports the study's finding that intrinsic motivation plays a key role in the development of science process skills. When students are interested and motivated from within, they are more likely to observe carefully, question critically, and participate actively in experiments. Also, it agrees with Abas and Marasigan (2020), which explained that science motivation is essential for preparing learners to engage in meaningful, hands-on scientific learning. They highlighted the role of simulation and laboratory-based tasks in developing learner enthusiasm and process-oriented thinking. Their research aligns with this study's findings that highly motivated learners display stronger science process skills. When teachers nurture this motivation, learners become more involved in scientific exploration and skill development. While Choirunnisa, et al., (2021) provided the conceptual foundation for this study's independent variables. The significant relationships found in this research, especially for career motivation and self-efficacy, reflect the multidimensional structure of motivation that they outlined. This supports the finding that not all domains are equally predictive of science process skills. Moreover, Mirana (2019) found that learners often have a positive attitude toward science but still struggle to develop science process skills due to lack of inquiry-based teaching. She emphasized that meaningful motivation must be paired with opportunities for practical engagement in science. This complements the present study's conclusion that motivation—particularly intrinsic and

career-related—must be translated into action through hands-on experiences. Without motivating environments and sufficient resources, learner engagement cannot effectively translate into skill mastery. Additionally, Sulistri (2019) argued that science process skills develop best when students integrate knowledge, attitudes, and hands-on practices. She pointed out that critical thinking and scientific inquiry evolve through meaningful learning experiences, not just theoretical knowledge or discipline. This aligns with the study's result showing that self-determination alone did not significantly influence SPS. Motivation must be supported by application-based learning to effectively enhance scientific competencies. Further, Vygotsky's socio-cultural Theory posits that learning is socially constructed, and motivation is enhanced through interaction with peers and teachers. In this context, learners develop confidence and motivation by receiving feedback, asking questions, and engaging collaboratively. These factors reinforce self-efficacy, which was shown in the study as a significant predictor of science process skills. Social and cultural dynamics thus play a foundational role in transforming motivation into measurable scientific ability. Furthermore, De Borja and Marasigan (2020) emphasized the significance of laboratory instruction in increasing learners' academic interest and achievement. They found that motivating environments paired with accessible scientific tools enhance student focus and performance. This supports the study's findings where grade motivation emerged as the strongest predictor of science process skills. Learners who are motivated by academic results tend to engage more deeply in scientific processes and achieve higher skill levels.

The study highlights that learners exhibit a strong and consistent motivation across various dimensions, with internal passion and personal

interest driving their engagement the most. This suggests that their learning is deeply influenced by factors beyond external rewards, fostering

Table 1. Summary of Science Motivation

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Intrinsic Motivation	4.52	Extremely Extensive
Career Motivation	4.21	Extremely Extensive
Self-Determination	4.16	Very Extensive
Self-Efficacy	4.11	Very Extensive
Grade Motivation	4.14	Very Extensive
Overall Mean	4.23	Extremely Extensive

a genuine commitment to growth and mastery. Additionally, the emphasis on career motivation reflects how learners are mindful of their future opportunities, which likely encourages sustained effort and goal-setting. Even though some motivational aspects show slightly lower ratings, the overall pattern indicates a supportive environment that nurtures both personal and academic aspirations.

3.2. *Science Process Skills in terms of Observing*—Presented in Table 2 are data on the Summary of the Science Process Skills. It obtained an overall mean rating of 4.29, which is Extremely Extensive and always evident, is distributed by the indicators, except with communicating indicator with very extensive descriptive equivalent. They were presented with the corresponding mean as follows: observing (4.38), measuring (4.39), inferring (4.34), experiment-

ing (4.22), and communicating (4.11). All four indicators were consistently rated at the highest descriptive level of “Extremely Extensive”, while only 1 indicator got the descriptive equivalent of “Very Extensive”. The results show that learners consistently exhibit highly developed science process skills across most areas, particularly in observing, measuring, inferring, and experimenting. These skills are clearly evident and demonstrate a strong foundation in conducting scientific inquiry. While communicating skills are also well-developed, they are slightly less pronounced compared to the other areas, indicating some room for growth in effectively sharing scientific information. Comprehensively, the findings reflect a robust and well-rounded mastery of key science processes among the learners.

Table 2. Summary of the Science Process Skills

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Observing	4.38	Extremely Extensive
Measuring	4.39	Extremely Extensive
Inferring	4.34	Extremely Extensive
Experimenting	4.22	Extremely Extensive
Communicating	4.11	Very Extensive
Overall Mean	4.29	Extremely Extensive

Tanti and colleagues (2020) defined science process skills as core competencies required for effective scientific inquiry and problem-solving. Their study emphasized the importance of observing, inferring, measuring, and communicating in science learning. This aligns directly with the dependent variables used in this study and the high performance observed among learners across these indicators. Their findings reinforce the importance of embedding these skills in science education to foster critical and analytical thinking. Haider and Muhammad (2020) demonstrated that students taught using inquiry-based methods exhibited significantly stronger science process skills than those taught through traditional lectures. Their study underscores the importance of motivating instructional strategies that prioritize active participation and experimentation. This supports the present findings that science motivation, especially intrinsic and self-efficacy, are critical for engaging learners in scientific practices. Well-designed motivational environments are thus essential to skill development. Gecain (2022) proposed that science process skills should not be isolated but integrated into all science instruction for them to be effectively acquired. He noted that lesson planning should revolve around scientific skills development and not just theoretical content. This supports the high skill levels reported in this study and the idea that sustained motivation leads to meaningful process skills application. The recommendation to benchmark SPS in planning directly supports this research's advocacy for motivation-integrated instruction.

Therefore, there is a significant relationship between the science motivation and science process skills of learners. The higher the value of science motivation, the greater the value of the science process skills is or the lesser the value of the science motivation means the less the value of the science process skills is. The signif-

3.3. Relationship Between Science Motivation and Science Process Skills—Table 3 presented the data on the significant relationship between science motivation and science process skills in public elementary schools, as measured by Pearson's r . The computed r -value of 0.68 indicates a high degree of relationship or substantial. The p -value of 0.00 is less than the alpha value of 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis is rejected at the significance level. The findings reveal that the independent and dependent variables are statistically significant. Hence, there was a significant relationship between School Environment and Teachers' Commitment. The results further suggest that school environment can make a significant difference in the teachers' commitment. This implies that all participants agreed that the quality of the school environment plays an important role in shaping and enhancing teachers' commitment. Consequently, the school environment acts as a guiding factor that motivates and directs teachers' dedication, ultimately contributing to a more positive and effective learning experience for learners. The Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.980 suggests a substantial positive relationship between science motivation and science process skills. The p -value of 0.000, which is below the significance level of 0.05, indicates that this relationship is statistically significant. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. The result implies that learners whose science motivation is effectively addressed by teachers tend to show higher science process skills achievement.

icant relationship between science motivation and science process skills found in this study supports the work of Duban et al., (2019), who highlighted that motivation plays a crucial role in enhancing students' engagement and proficiency in scientific inquiry. They argued that motivated learners are more likely to actively

Table 3. Relationship Between Science Motivation and Science Process Skills

Variables	Pearson- <i>r</i>	Degree of Correlation	P-value	Decision
Science Motivation (X) vs. Science Process Skills (Y)	0.980	Very High	0.000	Reject H ₀

Note: Significant when $P < 0.05$

participate in science process skills such as observing, measuring, and experimenting, which are essential for meaningful learning. This connection accentuated that fostering science motivation can directly improve learners’ ability to apply critical scientific skills. Thus, the findings affirm that enhancing motivation is a key factor in developing strong science process skills, ultimately leading to deeper understanding and better performance in science education.

3.4. On the Indicators of Science Motivation that Significantly Influences the Science Process Skills—Presented in Table 4 is the result of the linear regression analysis conducted to determine which indicators of science motivation significantly influence the science process skills of Grade 6 learners. The regression model was found to be statistically significant, with

The findings align with Glynn et al. (2011), who emphasized that intrinsic motivation plays a key role in increasing learners’ engagement in scientific tasks, fostering curiosity and deeper participation in experimental learning. The strong influence of career motivation is also consistent with Osborne and Collins (2001), who noted that learners with clear science-related goals are more likely to persist in developing investigative skills. Interestingly, self-efficacy had a negative coefficient, indicating an inverse relationship, possibly due to overconfidence or lack of alignment between perceived ability and actual performance, as Zimmerman and Schunk

an F-value of 28.02 and a p-value < 0.001 , indicating the robustness of the model in predicting the dependent variable. The model yielded an R² value of 0.761, suggesting that 76.1% of the variance in science process skills can be explained by the five domains of science motivation: intrinsic motivation, career motivation, self-determination, self-efficacy, and grade motivation. Among these predictors, grade motivation showed the highest standardized beta coefficient ($= 0.113$), followed by self-efficacy ($= 0.103$), career motivation ($= 0.076$), and intrinsic motivation ($= 0.034$), all of which significantly contributed to the model ($p < 0.05$). Self-determination, however, did not show a statistically significant influence on science process skills ($p = 0.695$), and thus the null hypothesis for this indicator was retained.

(2004) suggested. The positive impact of grade motivation corroborates Wolters’ (2004) claim that academic incentives can drive learners to perform better, especially when science tasks are linked to performance assessments. On the other hand, the non-significant influence of self-determination reflects Deci and Ryan’s (1985) argument that autonomy alone is insufficient without proper environmental and instructional support. Overall, the findings reinforce the importance of integrating motivational strategies in science teaching to enhance learners’ acquisition of science process skills. These findings highlight that learners who are intrinsically in-

Table 4. Linear Regression Analysis on the Indicators of Science Motivation that Significantly Influence Science Process Skills

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	Decision
H ₀₁	(Intercept)			
H ₀₂	(Intercept)			
—	Intrinsic Motivation	0.176	0.034	Reject H ₀
—	Career Motivation	0.505	0.076	Reject H ₀
—	Self-Determination	0.044	0.091	Accept H ₀
—	Self-Efficacy	-0.260	0.103	Reject H ₀
—	Grade Motivation	0.568	0.113	Reject H ₀
R²	0.761			
F-value	28.02			
p-value	0.000			

**Significant at p < 0.05*

terested in science, motivated by future career benefits, confident in their scientific abilities, and focused on achieving high grades are more likely to demonstrate stronger science process skills. The high R² value underscores the critical role of motivational factors in developing learners’ scientific inquiry and reasoning abilities. The relationship between motivation and

process skills illustrates the importance of cultivating both cognitive and affective domains in science education. By fostering these motivational components, educators can enhance learners’ capacity to perform authentic scientific practices, thereby promoting deeper understanding and improved academic outcomes in the sciences.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the focal points of the research, focusing on the statistical results and corresponding interpretations of the data collected. It includes a summary of the key findings and provides comprehensive conclusions and recommendations anchored on the study’s objectives.

4.1. Findings—The study investigated the relationship between science motivation and science process skills among grade 6 learners in Lupon, West District, Davao Oriental, in accordance with their teachers, utilizing a quantitative correlational approach. Science motivation was assessed through five domains: intrinsic motivation, career motivation, self-determination, self-efficacy, and grade motivation. While science process skills were examined through observing, measuring, inferring, experimenting, and communicating. The results revealed that

learners exhibited high levels of science motivation, particularly in intrinsic and grade motivation, which indicates that students found science learning engaging and were motivated to perform well academically. This motivational profile contributed positively to the development of their science process skills. Moreover, learners demonstrated extensive proficiency in science process skills, especially in measuring and observing. These skills were strongly evident in learners who were highly motivated and actively engaged in scientific tasks, confirming the

importance of fostering motivation to support effective science instruction. The statistical findings also showed that there was a very strong positive relationship between science motivation and science process skills, highlighting that when learners are well-motivated, whether by interest, confidence, or academic goals they tend to perform better in scientific investigations and practical tasks.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the overall findings of this research, the following conclusions were drawn: The findings of the study revealed that according to the teachers, learners in Lupon West District exhibit a high level of science motivation, particularly in the area of intrinsic motivation. Learners showed enthusiasm, curiosity, and a genuine interest in learning science, which contributed significantly to their overall engagement. This high intrinsic drive suggests that science is perceived not only as a school subject but as a meaningful and enjoyable pursuit by the learners. Science process skills were also found to be highly developed among the learners, with measuring and observing emerging as the most prominent indicators. These skills were consistently rated as “Extremely Extensive,” indicating that learners are proficient in essential tasks such as data collection, experimental setup, and critical observation. Such findings point to a learning environment where practical engagement and scientific inquiry are actively encouraged and supported. The study also established a strong positive and statistically significant relationship between science motivation and science process skills. Learners who were more motivated, whether by interest, confidence, or academic goals, demonstrated higher levels of science process skills. This confirms that fostering science motivation is a key strategy for improving learners’ practical competencies in scientific thinking and experimentation. Furthermore, several domains of science motivation were identified as significant predictors of science process skills,

namely grade motivation, self-efficacy, career motivation, and intrinsic motivation. Among these, grade motivation had the strongest influence, suggesting that learners are especially driven by performance outcomes and academic achievement. However, self-determination did not significantly contribute to the prediction of science process skills, indicating that effort alone, without appropriate structure and engagement, may not translate into improved scientific performance. Overall, the results emphasized the fundamental role of science motivation in enhancing learners’ scientific capabilities. By cultivating various types of motivation, academic, emotional, and future-oriented, educators can strengthen the foundation of science process skills among learners. These findings provide valuable insight for schools, teachers, and policymakers aiming to improve science education through targeted motivational and instructional strategies.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were offered for consideration:

Learners Learners be continuously encouraged to explore science with genuine curiosity and purpose. Providing learners with opportunities for hands-on, inquiry-based activities can further enhance their science process skills. Motivation can be cultivated through meaningful classroom experiences that connect scientific concepts to real-life situations, increasing students’ intrinsic interest and sense of purpose in science learning. Teachers Teachers are encouraged to adopt instructional strategies that explicitly integrate motivational factors such as academic recognition, relevance to future careers, and confidence-building activities. Since grade motivation and self-efficacy were found to significantly influence learners’ science process skills, educators should reinforce students’ belief in their abilities through constructive feedback, performance tracking, and encouraging goal-setting. Implementing varied assessment

methods and emphasizing collaborative learning can also support the development of both motivation and process skills. School Administrators School administrators are advised to support science instruction by investing in adequate laboratory resources and learning materials that allow learners to perform scientific tasks with accuracy and confidence. Facilitating professional development for teachers on how to effectively integrate science motivation into their pedagogy is equally essential. School leadership should also prioritize the creation of motivating classroom environments that promote academic excellence and scientific curiosity. Department of Education The Department of Education is encouraged to strengthen the implementation of science programs that promote both motivation and process skills among elementary learners. Curriculum enhancements should ensure that motivational domains are not treated in isolation but are embedded within performance-based sci-

ence instruction. It is further recommended that policies on teacher training and instructional supervision emphasize motivation-driven teaching practices and the consistent application of inquiry-based learning approaches. Future Researchers Future researchers may consider conducting studies that track the influence of science motivation over time or across different learning environments. Comparative studies between districts or regions may also yield insights into how contextual factors affect learners' science motivation and skill development. Additionally, qualitative research focusing on learners' perspectives could deepen understanding of how motivation evolves in relation to instructional methods and school environments. These follow-up studies would provide more comprehensive data that can help educators and policymakers further enhance science education in elementary schools.

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